

Milestone: M3.1: Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided

Lead Participant: UNIPD

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Date Of Completion: 18/10/2024

Means of Verification

[M3.1 Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

- UNIPD: Adel Bouhraoua, Federica Quaglia, Silvio Tosatto
- ATHENA RC: Thanasis Vergoulis, Maria Makaronidou
- WP3 members

Next action steps

- Further define and expand implementation aspects in the deliverable D3.1 "Report on credit and software management plan implementation"

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